

ADVANCED FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN ORGANIZING STUDENT INDEPENDENT EDUCATION

¹Khimmataliev Dustnazar Omonovich, ²Abdurakhmanova Dinorakhan Sukhrob qizi,

³Usarboeva Dildora Unarboy qizi

¹Doctor of pedagogic sciences, professor

^{2,3}1st-year Masters in "Pedagogy and Psychology"

^{1,2,3}Chirchik State Pedagogical University

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Abstract. *Taking into account that independent education is controlled by the person himself, with this activity, a person can freely and at any time choose the resources and use them from the point of view of purpose, means, and content.*

The main motives and indicators of independent education, the main criteria of independent education are highlighted in the article.

Keywords: *experience, ability, knowledge, development, skill, tool.*

Introduction

One of the important factors of training qualified personnel is to increase the quality and efficiency of education. Modern methods, forms and tools of teaching, game technologies, problem-based teaching, in particular, non-traditional methods of independent education play an important role in improving the quality and efficiency of education. This requires conducting scientific-pedagogical research on the popularization and improvement of advanced foreign experiences in the organization of independent education in higher education institutions.

Taking into account that independent education is controlled by the person himself, with this activity, a person can freely and at any time choose the resources and use them from the point of view of purpose, means, and content.

In the psychological and pedagogical literature, a lot of attention is paid to the development of independent learning skills. In particular, in the works of N.F. Talyzina, the role and place of independence in the formation of human personality is widely explained [3]. The need and importance of organizing independent education of students was considered by V.V. Davydov and others [1].

Despite the many works devoted to the organization of independent education of students, the problem of teaching students to acquire independent knowledge is still open. Therefore, the activity and independence of students in learning has become one of the leading didactic principles. Students determine the goals and tasks that make up the content of independent education, depending on the strength and motivational reasons that arouse interest in independent education. This can be expressed as follows:

1. Political independent education, modern reality and the attitude towards them, which are considered important in conducting independent activities;

2. Professional independent education in the preparatory period aimed at carrying out activities in the chosen direction, mastering the student's independent education;

3. Independent education directed to further study of academic subjects, personal life plans, personal interest;

4. Independent education related to the development of one's talents and hobbies.

5. Independent education aimed at training one's own character.

Professional independent education is the main factor in the development of a person and serves as a description of his ability to work independently in his future activities. The content of independent education will depend on the ability to find opportunities for independent education, not directly affecting the nature of work, but indirectly. Self-directed learning is a means of determining the student's path in the future, and allows the student to assess his own capabilities. Although the student does not have a clearly expressed need, every person definitely has a non-biological need to satisfy himself, to express himself, to show his existence.

Method

The teacher should direct the activities of independent improvement of his knowledge to a specific goal and in order to achieve this goal, he must comply with the following conditions.

1. The content of self-improvement of one's own knowledge should be adapted to the specific conditions of the training workshop of the educational institution where the pedagogical practice in the specialty of the teacher is taking place, the conditions of the practice, and the requirements.

2. Based on a certain goal and in a certain order, the teacher should develop the following qualities in himself:

- to deeply feel and understand the aspirations and interests of students, to be able to take into account their spiritual needs;

- establishing an emotional connection with students, actively influencing aspects of their mental, moral and practical activities.

3. The teacher must independently study the list of questions on general pedagogy, psychology, occupational hygiene and physiology, technical and technological sciences.

4. The teacher should choose the most effective methods and ways of the work system to improve his pedagogical skills, and operate by correctly selecting the technological process and technical objects.

5. It is appropriate for the teacher to use the forms of improving his knowledge, to perform practical exercises, taking into account the specific conditions and in accordance with them individually or together with the team.

6. It is necessary for the teacher to organize the improvement of his knowledge in the form of constant creative research and direct it to a certain goal.

For this he:

- tends to manage the process of creative research;

- it should be remembered that the effectiveness of creative research depends on the pedagogical, psychological and theoretical preparation of the teacher.

According to pedagogue scientist N.A. Muslimov, "Independent education" means the organization of subjective, regular, independent and autonomous activities of the educational process for the development of concepts, skills and competencies of knowledge acquisition [2].

One of the main motivations for independent education is the desire for something new, unknown, which is related to external stimulation and internal qualities of the individual. The ability to usefully implement the experience gained in the labor market and the ability to think creatively are the main incentives for creative assimilation of knowledge; Another incentive is the need to understand the objective reality more deeply and, of course, to understand that the knowledge acquired by students is the basis of social, personal and professional development.

Table 1

Indicators of independent education

Criteria	Signs	Indicators
Manifestation of creativity	- Emergence of interest in learning; - Formation of mental abilities	Interest in learning, imagination, activity in games, reading, drawing, etc
The need for self-awareness	- Self-development ability; - Taking advantage of their opportunities	Activating thought processes, this is a manifestation of age-appropriate interest
Pursuit of systematic independent education	- High level of self-awareness - Determining the level of future activity, preparation and duration	Determining methods of achieving the final result based on personal interests
Manifestation of creative thinking	- Transforming acquired knowledge into new views, ideas, imaginations; - High probability operation	Independence in the selection and acquisition of knowledge, high efficiency in the acquisition of new material
Manifestation of creative activity	Determining the future activity, its size and duration of preparation	Making practical decisions
Improving the system of individual knowledge	- Training planning; - To determine the ways and means of achieving the goal	Increasing the efficiency of independent educational activities
Development of motives for future independent activity	- Future spiritual development; - Formation of emotional and freedom qualities	The influence of knowledge on the comprehensive development of the personality

Self-awareness in a reproductive form (repeating the material learned, completing tasks, etc.) is the first level of the process of creative learning and mastering. A high level of creative independence is the combination of previously learned and new material. The second stage is characterized by a high level of independence, the selected material is connected and restored with new methods of processing and analyzing the received information. The next, higher level of creative independence is determined by the student's ability to solve tasks, acquire new knowledge and acquire new skills using convenient methods of information search, selection and learning. The highest level of independent education is defined by independent formulation of problems and striving to solve them independently. The first two levels must be mastered to reach the last level. Creative thinking is also part of the process of acquiring sustainable skills for independent work. Talent is required for the manifestation of creative thinking, the process of acquiring knowledge, studying an interesting problem is related to creativity and thinking, and creative thinking skills are formed [4].

Results and discussion

The main criterion of independent education is the ability of students to plan their lessons. It is related to defining the purpose of their activity, ways and means of its implementation, and

planning personal affairs. When planning the scheme of the educational task, the sequence, the availability of certain labor tools, the organization of the workplace and the progress of the educational process are determined. Independent planning of such activities is carried out in three stages. The first, direction stage - the student's mind realizes, thinks and evaluates his possibilities, the appropriateness of achieving the goal. At this stage, there are opinions for and against the continuation of independent activity. If positive motives prevail, independent activity planning moves to the next stage - the stage of thinking about the conditions and state of future activities. In the last, third stage of planning, execution planning is carried out, that is, the activity system and the sequence of the task execution scheme are imagined. Students' planning of their work is inextricably linked with the development of self-control skills, i.e. monitoring the correctness of their actions, identifying and preventing deviations from the planned plan in time, regulating and correcting their actions, and achieving goals. Self-control is an important tool for independent performance of academic work [4].

Self-acquiring knowledge is the most distinctive feature of student activity in an educational institution, the basis of independent study and knowledge acquisition. The process of independent study and knowledge acquisition means independent preparation of students. Independent education of future bachelor-teachers is aimed at increasing the efficiency of work results in accordance with professional-pedagogical activities. In this, the future teacher analyzes the results of his work and determines the content of his professional pedagogical activity. The main goal of a teacher's independent education is to improve his professional pedagogical skills and achieve high achievements in his professional activity.

Summary

The process of teaching independent thinking is a key part of independent education. Many psychologists, in particular, N.F. Talyzina and others have conducted research with problems related to independent thinking [3].

In order to activate the process of independent learning, it is necessary to form the following characteristics in students:

- enthusiasm for independent education (motivation);
- independent learning qualifications and skills;
- the ability to learn independently.

Factors that actively encourage independent education include:

- direct active interest in independent activity;
- motives of moral aesthetic and spiritual satisfaction.

The stages of development of knowledge needs are:

- the stage of elementary scientific research activities (formation of the need for external impressions);
- the stage of formation of the need to know the world;
- the stage of formation of the need for training as an activity of acquiring the method of knowing;
- the stage of formation of orientation towards the selection of knowledge needs;
- the stage of developing the need for independent education.

Especially the last stage is important for research work. Because the formation of the need for independent study is important for students to become mature, well-rounded, qualified specialists in their field. Independent learning and control in the educational system is one of the

main factors of independent education. In getting independent education, first of all, it is necessary to form the need for independent work, free, creative activity in students.

According to the research of the psychologist A. Maslow, we can see a creative approach to this issue in the pyramid of human needs [5].

As it can be seen from this pyramid, as human needs increase, he strives for perfection (Figure 1). In order to reach maturity, the characteristics of activity, independence, and curiosity must be developed in students. In addition, future teachers in their practical activities are faced with such processes as a decrease in work ability, fatigue, exhaustion, work, and the order of rest. Therefore, the future teacher should have certain knowledge and skills in occupational hygiene and physiology.

1 - picture. Pyramid of human needs

In order for students to engage in independent learning, they should have the characteristics of independence, activity and curiosity (Figure 1). These three characteristics are interrelated and proportional to the motivational characteristics of self-directed learning. Independence means students' creative approach to solving problems, studying the subject and performing practical tasks independently. Activity means that students are actively and enthusiastically involved in the process. Curiosity means that students approach the process of acquiring knowledge, skills and competences with interest and aspiration.

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